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The Application of Digital Technologies for Business in Europe

It grew by 65.52% on average between 2016 and 2021

The Digital Technologies for Business variable is calculated as part of the Desi-Index. It is a variable consisting of a set of sub-variables or: Electronic Information Sharing, Social Media, Big Data, Cloud, Ai, ICT for Environmental Sustainability, E-Invoices. The variable is part of a larger variable macro or Integration of Digital Technologies. The data are available in the 2016-2021 period for 27 countries.

Ranking of European countries for the value of digital technologies for business in 2021. Finland is in the first place for the value of digital technologies for business with a value equal to 41.10 units, followed by Sweden with a value of 37.61 Unit and Denmark with a value of 36.45 units. In the middle of the standings there are Austria with a value of 26.95 units, Estonia with a value of 26.36 units and Spain with a value of 25.91 units. Bulgaria closes the ranking with a value of 17.06 units, followed by Poland with a value of 16.88 units and by Hungary with a value of 15.41 units.

Ranking of European countries by percentage variation of digital technologies for the business between 2016 and 2021. Estonia is in the first place for the value of the percentage variation of digital technologies for the business between 2016 and 2021 with a value of 113.54% or equal to an amount of 14.02 units, followed by Latvia with a variation of 109.00% equal to an amount of 10.38%, and from Italy with a variation of 97.37% equal to an absolute value of 14,26 units. In the middle of the standings there are Sweden with a value of 70.35% equal to an amount of 15.53 units, followed by Austria with a value of 68.13% equal to an amount of 10.92 units and from Luxembourg with a variation of an amount of 67.41% equal to an amount of 11.46 units. Greece closes the ranking with a percentage variation of 44.67% equal to an amount of 6.90 units, followed by Portugal with a variation of 40.79% equal to an amount of 7.42 units and by Slovakia with one variation of 35.63% equal to an amount of 5.00 units.

Clusterization with K-means algorithm. Below is a clusterization using the K-means algorithm optimized through the silhouette coefficient. The analysis shows the presence of two different Clusters or:

- Cluster 1: Romania, Estonia, Germany, Slovakia, Bulgaria, Cyprus, Italy, Latvia, Croatia, Poland, France, Czech Republic, Hungary, Greece, Austria;
- Cluster 2: Denmark, Malta, Belgium, Sweden, Netherlands, Ireland, Lithuania; Slovenia, Portugal, Finland, Luxembourg, Spain.

Calculating the value of the Clusters median it appears that the value of the median of the 2-C2 cluster is equal to 30.44, while the value of the 1-C1 cluster is equal to 22.33. The result is therefore the following system of the Clusters or: $C2 = 30.44 > C1 = 22.33$. From a geographical point of view, the contrast between the countries of Northern Europe is evident with the addition of Spain and Portugal, and the countries of the central-southern Europe.

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Network Analysis using Manhattan's distance. Using Manhattan's distance, 3 network structures are detected of which two are complex and one is simplified.

There is a complex network structure between the Czech Republic, France, Croatia, Cyprus, Italy, and Greece. Specifically:

- The Czech Republic has a link with France for a value of 0.092;
- France has a connection with the Czech Republic equal to an amount of 0.092 and with Croatia for a value of 0.091;
- Croatia has a connection with Greece for a value of 0.24, with Italy for an amount of 0.11, with Cyprus with a value of 0.2 and with France with a value equal to 0.091;
- Italy has a connection with Greece for a value of 0.24, with Croatia for a value of 0.11, with Cyprus for a value of 0.2;
- Cyprus has a connection with Italy for a value of 0.2 and with Croatia for a value of 0.2.

There is also a complex structure consisting of Portugal, Slovenia, Lithuania, and Ireland. Particularly:

- Portugal has a connection with Slovenia equal to an amount of 0.18;
- Slovenia has a connection with Portugal for a value of 0.18, with Ireland for a value of 0.15 and with Lithuania for a value of 0.21;
- Lithuania has a connection with Slovenia for a value of 0.21 units and with Ireland with a value of 0.07;
- Ireland has a connection with Lithuania for a value of 0.07 units and with Slovenia equal to an amount of 0.15 units.

In addition, there is a simple network structure between Estonia and Germany having a value of 0.16 units.

Machine Learning and Prediction. A prediction is made below using Machine Learning algorithms. In particular, nine different Machine Learning algorithms are compared according to their ability to maximize R² and minimize MSE, RMSE and Mae. The algorithms were trained with a leather installment value of 80%. The analysis expressed the existence of the following system of algorithms for predictive efficiency or:

- Linear Regression with a payoff value of 6;
- SGD with a payoff value of 7;
- KNN with a payoff value of 12;
- Random Forest with a payoff value of 15;
- Gradient Boosting with a payoff value of 20;
- Adaboost with a payoff value of 26;
- Tree with a payoff value of 27;
- SVM with a payoff value of 31;
- Neural Network with a payoff value of 36.

Therefore, by applying the algorithm with the best performances or Linear Regression it is possible to predict a reduction on average for the countries considered equal to -0.04% of the value of the

digital Technologies for Business. Specifically, the algorithm predicts that the countries that will have greater growth in the sense of digitization of business are Portugal with a value of +12.6%, Slovakia with a value of +11.84%, Bulgaria with + 11.84% and Romania with a value of +11.39%. The countries for which the linear regression algorithm predicts a backward of the application of digital technologies to business are Denmark with -7.96%, Croatia with a value equal to -8.26%, Italy with a value equal to -23.99%, and Estonia with -24.86%.

Under and over the European Union Mean. In addition, algorithms can be used to calculate the probability of the upper countries the value of the European average which is equal in 221 to 25.33. Therefore, if in 2021 the value of the variable of interest is higher than the European average a value of 1 is attributed in the opposite case of a value of 0. Through this analysis a new analysis is carried out for the comparison of the performance of the algorithms this time considered in accuracy terms. The algorithms were trained with 80% of the available data. The analysis shows that in terms of accuracy the following system of algorithms or:

- Gradient Boosting and AdaBoost with an accuracy equal to 1;
- Tree with an accuracy equal to 0.96;
- Neural Network and KNN with an accuracy equal to 0.93;
- SGD, SVM and Random Forest with an accuracy of 0.89.

Conclusions. The analysis shows an increasing trend of the application of digital technologies for business in European countries. However, there are large gaps in terms of growth between the areas of northern Europe and the areas of the central-southern Europe. The analysis in Clusters and the network analysis confirms the idea that there are groups of countries strictly connected in the performance in terms of digital technologies for business. The prediction with Machine Learning algorithms highlights what will probably be the Losers and the Winners in the application of digital technology for business in Europe. It is likely that this value however grows or tends to converge towards the European average, even if these improvements are lacking in being indifferent to the application of European economic policies.

Declarations

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Appendix

Feature 1	MSE	RMSE	MAE	R2
1 SGD	0	0.00000	0.0158079	0.3763164
2 Linear Regression	0.00103923	0.0037259	0.00000	1.00000
3 kNN	0.0122525	0.0400940	0.0580786	0.9957875
4 Random Forest	0.0164046	0.0521626	0.0577293	0.3703877
5 Gradient Boosti...	0.0214062	0.0659323	0.0764192	0.3682815
6 AdaBoost	0.0339672	0.0977645	0.1896070	0.3635229
7 Tree	0.0391443	0.1099141	0.1090830	0.3615727
8 SVM	0.0905411	0.2133485	0.1801747	0.3423044
9 Neural Network	1	1.00000	1.00000	0.00000

<i>Predizione attraverso l'utilizzo dell'algorithmo Linear Regression</i>									
Country	2021	Predictions	Var ass	Var Per	Country	2021	Predictions	Var ass	Var Per
<i>Finland</i>	41,10	42,37	1,27	3,09	<i>Lettonia</i>	19,91	20,12	0,21	1,05
<i>Ireland</i>	28,92	29,48	0,56	1,92	<i>Romania</i>	18,10	20,16	2,06	11,39
<i>France</i>	24,46	25,40	0,94	3,85	<i>Croazia</i>	25,38	23,28	-2,10	-8,26
<i>Portugal</i>	25,62	28,85	3,23	12,60	<i>Spagna</i>	25,91	27,26	1,35	5,21
<i>Austria</i>	26,95	27,41	0,46	1,70	<i>Slovacchia</i>	19,04	21,29	2,25	11,84
<i>Grecia</i>	22,34	23,16	0,82	3,67	<i>Malta</i>	36,03	34,77	-1,26	-3,51
<i>Lituania</i>	27,91	29,91	2,00	7,15	<i>Svezia</i>	37,61	35,10	-2,51	-6,67
<i>Lussemburgo</i>	28,47	29,71	1,24	4,36	<i>Polandia</i>	16,88	17,42	0,53	3,16
<i>Ungheria</i>	15,41	15,41	0,00	0,02	<i>Estonia</i>	26,36	19,81	-6,55	-24,86
<i>Slovenia</i>	27,89	30,31	2,42	8,69	<i>Germania</i>	22,83	22,71	-0,12	-0,54
<i>Belgio</i>	31,97	31,49	-0,48	-1,49	<i>Italia</i>	28,91	21,98	-6,94	-23,99
<i>Cipro</i>	21,70	21,76	0,06	0,26	<i>Paesi Bassi</i>	34,28	33,74	-0,54	-1,58
<i>Bulgaria</i>	17,06	19,01	1,96	11,48	<i>Danimarca</i>	36,45	33,55	-2,90	-7,96
<i>Repubblica Ceca</i>	23,53	25,28	1,74	7,41	<i>Media</i>	25,95	27,11	1,16	4,46

Ranking degli algoritmi per capacità predittiva						
Rank	Algoritmo	MSE	RMSE	MAE	R2	Totale
1	<i>Linear Regression</i>	2	2	1	1	6
2	<i>SGD</i>	1	1	2	3	7
3	<i>kNN</i>	3	3	4	2	12
4	<i>Random Forest</i>	4	4	3	4	15
5	<i>Gradient Boosting</i>	5	5	5	5	20
6	<i>AdaBoost</i>	6	6	8	6	26
7	<i>Tree</i>	7	7	6	7	27
8	<i>SVM</i>	8	8	7	8	31
9	<i>Neural Network</i>	9	9	9	9	36

Digital Technologies per il Business nel 2021.

Variazione percentuale utilizzo delle tecnologie digitali per il business.

Rank	Country	Var Ass	Var Per	Rank	Country	Var Ass	Var Per
1	<i>Estonia</i>	★ 14,02	★ 113,54	15	<i>Finland</i>	★ 16,35	★ 66,04
2	<i>Latvia</i>	★ 10,38	★ 109,00	16	<i>Hungary</i>	★ 5,92	★ 62,36
3	<i>Italy</i>	★ 14,26	★ 97,37	17	<i>Ireland</i>	★ 10,52	★ 57,14
4	<i>Germany</i>	★ 10,55	★ 85,95	18	<i>Spain</i>	★ 9,35	★ 56,49
5	<i>Malta</i>	★ 16,56	★ 85,00	19	<i>Lithuania</i>	★ 9,73	★ 53,49
6	<i>Poland</i>	★ 7,68	★ 83,54	20	<i>Slovenia</i>	★ 9,43	★ 51,12
7	<i>France</i>	★ 10,57	★ 76,16	21	<i>Cyprus</i>	★ 7,07	★ 48,37
8	<i>Denmark</i>	★ 15,74	★ 76,05	22	<i>Romania</i>	★ 5,86	★ 47,89
9	<i>Croatia</i>	★ 10,68	★ 72,71	23	<i>Bulgaria</i>	★ 5,49	★ 47,53
10	<i>Czechia</i>	★ 9,76	★ 70,88	24	<i>Netherlands</i>	★ 11,02	★ 47,37
11	<i>Belgium</i>	★ 13,25	★ 70,83	25	<i>Greece</i>	★ 6,90	★ 44,67
12	<i>Sweden</i>	★ 15,53	★ 70,35	26	<i>Portugal</i>	★ 7,42	★ 40,79
13	<i>Austria</i>	★ 10,92	★ 68,13	27	<i>Slovakia</i>	★ 5,00	★ 35,63
14	<i>Luxembourg</i>	★ 11,46	★ 67,41				

Utilizzo delle tecnologie digitali per il business nel 2021

Rank	Country	2021	Rank	Country	2021
1	<i>Finland</i>	★ 41,10	15	<i>Portugal</i>	★ 25,62
2	<i>Sweden</i>	★ 37,61	16	<i>Croatia</i>	★ 25,38
3	<i>Denmark</i>	★ 36,45	17	<i>France</i>	★ 24,46
4	<i>Malta</i>	★ 36,03	18	<i>Czechia</i>	★ 23,53
5	<i>Netherlands</i>	★ 34,28	19	<i>Germany</i>	★ 22,83
6	<i>Belgium</i>	★ 31,97	20	<i>Greece</i>	★ 22,34
7	<i>Ireland</i>	★ 28,92	21	<i>Cyprus</i>	★ 21,70
8	<i>Italy</i>	★ 28,91	22	<i>Latvia</i>	★ 19,91
9	<i>Luxembourg</i>	★ 28,47	23	<i>Slovakia</i>	★ 19,04
10	<i>Lithuania</i>	★ 27,91	24	<i>Romania</i>	★ 18,10
11	<i>Slovenia</i>	★ 27,89	25	<i>Bulgaria</i>	★ 17,06
12	<i>Austria</i>	★ 26,95	26	<i>Poland</i>	★ 16,88
13	<i>Estonia</i>	★ 26,36	27	<i>Hungary</i>	★ 15,41
14	<i>Spain</i>	★ 25,91			

